

APPENDIX

A checklist of the Muscidae (Diptera) of Georgia

Subfamily Atherigoninae

Genus *Atherigona* Rondani, 1856

Atherigona varia (Meigen, 1826)

Subfamily Reinwardtiinae

Genus *Eginia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Eginia ocypterata (Meigen, 1826)

Genus *Muscina* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Muscina levida (Harris, 1780)

Muscina minor (Portschinsky, 1881)

Muscina pascuorum (Meigen, 1826)

Muscina prolapsa (Harris, 1780)

Muscina stabulans (Fallén, 1817)

Subfamily Azeliinae

Genus *Azelia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Azelia cilipes (Haliday, 1838)

Azelia gibbera (Meigen, 1826)

Azelia nebulosa Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Azelia zetterstedtii Rondani, 1866

Genus *Drymeia* Meigen, 1826

Drymeia caucasica (Schnabl in Schnabl, Dziedzicki, 1911)

Drymeia fasciculata (Stein, 1916)

Drymeia fratercula Pont, 2022

Drymeia setibasis (Huckett, 1965)

Drymeia sororcula Pont, 2022

Drymeia vicana (Harris, 1780)

Genus *Huckettomyia* Pont et Shinonaga, 1970

Huckettomyia secunda Pont et Vikhrev, 2010

Genus *Hydrotaea* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Hydrotaea albipuncta (Zetterstedt, 1845)

Hydrotaea armipes (Fallén, 1825)

Hydrotaea borussica Stein, 1899

Hydrotaea dentipes (Fabricius, 1805)

Hydrotaea diabolus (Harris, 1780)

Hydrotaea floccosa Macquart, 1835

Hydrotaea ignava (Harris, 1780)

Hydrotaea irritans (Fallén, 1823)

Hydrotaea meridionalis Portschinsky, 1882

Hydrotaea meteorica (Linnaeus, 1758)

Hydrotaea militaris (Meigen, 1826)

Hydrotaea pilitibia Stein, 1916

Hydrotaea velutina Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Genus *Thricops* Rondani, 1856

Thricops bukowskii (Ringdahl, 1934)

Thricops calcaratus (Portschinsky, 1881)

Thricops cunctans (Meigen, 1826)

Thricops diaphanus (Wiedemann, 1817)

Thricops foveolatus (Zetterstedt, 1845)

Thricops genarum (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Thricops innocuus (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Thricops longipes (Zetterstedt, 1845)

Thricops nigrifrons (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Thricops nigritellus (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Thricops rostratus (Meade, 1882)

Thricops semicinereus (Wiedemann, 1817)

Thricops tomkovichii Vikhrev in Vikhrev, Sorokina, 2009

Thricops vaderi Savage, 2003

Subfamily Muscinae

Genus *Dasyphora* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Dasyphora albofasciata (Macquart in Webb, Berthelot, 1839)

Dasyphora penicillata (Egger, 1865)

Dasyphora pratorum (Meigen, 1826)

Genus *Eudasyphora* Townsend, 1911

Eudasyphora zimini (Hennig, 1963)

Genus *Mesembrina* Meigen, 1826

Mesembrina meridiana (Linnaeus, 1758)

Mesembrina mystacea (Linnaeus, 1758)

Genus *Morellia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Morellia aenescens Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Morellia hortorum (Fallén, 1817)

Morellia podagrica (Loew, 1857)

Genus *Musca* Linnaeus, 1758

Musca autumnalis De Geer, 1776

Musca domestica Linnaeus, 1758

Musca larvipara Portschinsky, 1910

Musca osiris Wiedemann, 1830

Musca tempestiva Fallén, 1817

Genus *Neomyia* Walker, 1859

Neomyia cornicina (Fabricius, 1781)

Neomyia viridescens (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Genus *Polietes* Rondani, 1866

Polietes domitor (Harris, 1780)

Polietes lardarius (Fabricius, 1781)

Genus *Pyrellia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Pyrellia vivida Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Ziminellia Nihei et de Carvalho, 2007

Ziminellia asetosa (Baranoff, 1925)

Ziminellia simplex (Loew, 1857)

Subfamily Stomoxyinae

Genus *Haematobia* Le Peletier et Audinet-Serville in Latreille, Le Peletier, Audinet-Serville et Guérin-Méneville, 1828

Haematobia irritans (Linnaeus, 1758)

Genus *Haematobosca* Bezzi, 1907

Haematobosca stimulans (Meigen, 1824)

Genus *Stomoxys* Geoffroy, 1762

Stomoxys calcitrans (Linnaeus, 1758)

Subfamily Phaoniinae

Genus *Helina* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Helina abdominalis (Zetterstedt, 1846)
Helina annosa (Zetterstedt, 1838)
Helina cinerella (Wulp, 1867)
Helina concolor (Czerny, 1900)
Helina cothurnata (Rondani, 1866)
Helina edita Pont, 2012
Helina evecta (Harris, 1780)
Helina fratercula (Zetterstedt, 1845)
Helina impuncta (Fallén, 1824)
Helina lasiophthalma (Macquart, 1835)
Helina obscurata (Meigen, 1826)
Helina reversio (Harris, 1780)
Helina sexmaculata (Preyssl, 1791)
Helina subvittata (Séguy, 1923)
Helina tetrastigma (Meigen, 1826)
Helina trivittata (Zetterstedt, 1860)

Genus *Lophosceles* Ringdahl, 1922

Lophosceles cinereiventris (Zetterstedt, 1845)

Genus *Phaonia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Phaonia adriani Zinoviev, 1994
Phaonia angelicae (Scopoli, 1763)
Phaonia consobrina (Zetterstedt, 1838)
Phaonia errans (Meigen, 1826)
Phaonia fuscata (Fallén, 1825)
Phaonia gergetica Zinoviev, 1994
Phaonia gobertii (Mik, 1881)
Phaonia halterata (Stein, 1893)
Phaonia hybrida (Schnabl, 1888)
Phaonia incana (Wiedemann, 1817)
Phaonia kobica Schnabl in Schnabl, Dziedzicki, 1911
Phaonia kowarzii (Schnabl, 1887)
Phaonia laeta (Fallén, 1823)
Phaonia magnicornis (Zetterstedt, 1845)
Phaonia mediterranea Hennig, 1963
Phaonia mystica (Meigen, 1826)
Phaonia opalina Schnabl in Schnabl, Dziedzicki, 1911
[unrecognised]
Phaonia pallida (Fabricius, 1787)
Phaonia palpata (Stein, 1897)
Phaonia regalis (Stein, 1900)
Phaonia rufiventris (Scopoli, 1763)
Phaonia signata (Meigen, 1826)
Phaonia subventa (Harris, 1780)
Phaonia tiefii (Schnabl, 1888)
Phaonia trimaculata (Bouché, 1834)
Phaonia wahlbergi Ringdahl, 1930
Phaonia zugmayeriae (Schnabl, 1888)

Subfamily Mydaeinae

Genus *Graphomya* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Graphomya maculata (Scopoli, 1763)

Genus *Hebecnema* Schnabl, 1889

Hebecnema umbratica (Meigen, 1826)
Hebecnema vespertina (Fallén, 1823)

Genus *Mydaea* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Mydaea affinis Meade, 1891
Mydaea ancilla (Meigen, 1826)
Mydaea corni (Scopoli, 1763)
Mydaea detrita (Zetterstedt, 1845)
Mydaea humeralis Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830
Mydaea urbana (Meigen, 1826)

Genus *Myospila* Rondani, 1856

Myospila alpina Hendel, 1901
Myospila meditabunda (Fabricius, 1781)

Subfamily Coenosiinae

Tribe Limmophorini

Genus *Limmophora* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Limmophora caesia (Villeneuve, 1936)
Limmophora mediterranea Pont in Pont, Harutyunova,
Harutyunova et Werner, 2012
Limmophora pandellei Séguy, 1923
Limmophora pulchriceps (Loew, 1860)
Limmophora setinerva Schnabl in Schnabl, Dziedzicki, 1911
Limmophora tigrina (Am Stein, 1860)
Limmophora triangula (Fallén, 1825)

Genus *Lispe* Latreille, 1796

Lispe flavicincta Loew, 1847
Lispe nana Macquart, 1835
Lispe pygmaea Fallén, 1825
Lispe tentaculata (De Geer, 1776)

Genus *Spilogona* Schnabl, 1911

Spilogona nora Pont, 2013
Spilogona paradispar Pont, 2023
Spilogona taeniata (Stein, 1916)

Subfamily Coenosiinae

Tribe Coenosiini

Genus *Coenosia* Meigen, 1826

Coenosia agromyzina (Fallén, 1825)
Coenosia albicornis Meigen, 1826
Coenosia emiliae Lukashova, 1986
Coenosia femoralis (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)
Coenosia infantula Rondani, 1866
Coenosia mollicula (Fallén, 1825)
Coenosia nigridigita Rondani, 1866
Coenosia oligochaeta Hennig, 1961
Coenosia ozerovi Vikhrev, 2009
Coenosia pulicaria (Zetterstedt, 1845)
Coenosia ? pumila (Fallén, 1825)
Coenosia rufipalpis Meigen, 1826
Coenosia verralli Collin, 1953

Genus *Lispocephala* Pokorny, 1893

Lispocephala brachialis (Rondani, 1877)
Lispocephala erythrocerata (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)
Lispocephala pallipalpis (Zetterstedt, 1845)

Genus *Macrorchis* Rondani, 1877

Macrorchis meditata (Fallén, 1825)

Genus *Schoenomyza* Haliday, 1833

Schoenomyza litorella (Fallén, 1823)